

**MODELING AND ANALYSIS OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS
OF SHORT-FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC-MATRIX COMPOSITES**

Kazuro Kageyama and Tsu-Wei Chou
Department of Mechanical Engineering,
and Center for Composite Materials
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19716
USA

ABSTRACT

Toughening mechanisms of crack deflection and fiber pullout in short fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMC) are examined. The stress intensity factor of a deflected crack is analyzed by using the distributed dislocation method. The effects of closure force, load transfer and crack impediment are considered in the analysis. A mixed mode fracture criterion of CMC is applied to the mechanical model. Probabilities of crack deflection and fiber pullout are examined in a statistical model. Probability of failure of short fiber reinforced CMC is discussed by using the combined mechanical and statistical models.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMC) exhibit much enhanced fracture toughness as comparing to unreinforced ceramics. Major mechanisms of toughening are crack deflection and fiber pullout. The crack deflection around second phase particles has been analyzed by Faber et al.[1]. The fiber pullout in continuous fiber reinforced CMC has been analyzed by Marshall et al.[2]. However, combined toughening mechanisms of crack deflection and fiber pullout have been observed in SiC whisker reinforced CMC [3]. In the present paper, mechanical and statistical models of toughening of short fiber reinforced CMC are proposed. The crack deflection and fiber pullout are analyzed from a statistical viewpoint.

MECHANICAL AND STATISTICAL MODELS OF TOUGHENING

It is assumed that crack propagates in the matrix from a main crack by linking the microcracks as shown in Fig.1. The major mechanisms of toughening are the crack deflection and fiber pullout as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1 Crack propagation by linking microcracks.

Fig.2 Fiber pullout and crack deflection

l_s and θ in Fig.1 represent the length and angle, respectively, of a deflected crack. l_s is determined from a consideration of the process zone size, w , in the plane strain condition [4].

$$w = \frac{1}{3\pi} \left(\frac{K_{IC}}{\sigma_f} \right)^2 \tag{1}$$

K_{IC} and σ_f are the fracture toughness and tensile strength of composites, respectively. From the consideration of applicability of linear elastic fracture mechanics, l_s should be sufficiently larger than w . Hence, l_s is assumed to be $2w$ in the present analysis.

Fig.3 Kink from a main crack

Fig. 4 Statistical model

In order to examine the effects of crack deflection and fiber pullout on the microscopic loading system, a mechanical model of kinked crack as shown in Fig.3 is analyzed. For simplicity, the two dimensional deflection is assumed in the analysis. The fiber pullout forces are approximated by the continuous distribution of closure stress, S_b , on the upper and lower surfaces of the kink. $S_b =$ (average pullout force of

a fiber) \times (number of pullout fibers per unit area), and it is assumed to be constant on the kink. The stress intensity factors, \bar{K}_I and \bar{K}_{II} , at the tip of the kink are calculated from the mechanical model. The effects of the load transfer from matrix to fiber and the crack impediment are also approximately considered and an equivalent stress intensity factor, K_{eq} , is introduced as the mixed mode fracture criterion.

The crack deflects because of the inhomogeneity of the composite due to the distribution of fibers. A statistical model is introduced to explain the mechanism of crack deflection. In the case of SiC whisker /Al₂O₃ composites of Vf = 30%, for example, it has been reported that K_{IC} and σ_f are 8 MPa \sqrt{m} and 660 MPa, respectively, and that the average diameter and length of SiC whisker are 0.8 μ m and 25 μ m, respectively, [5]. From these values l_s is determined to be 30 μ m, and the average number of fibers intersecting the area of ($l_s \times l_s$) is found to be 268, as discussed below. Since there exist many fibers in the region, the crack deflection may be analyzed from the statistical point of view. It is also assumed in the present analysis that the pullout stress, S_b , is proportional to the density of intersecting fibers, s , which is a random variable. Then, S_b becomes also a random variable.

Once the distribution of fibers is determined, the statistical distribution of K_{eq} can be calculated by using the results of the mechanical model. The fracture criterion is,

$$K_{eq} \geq K_{cm} \quad (2)$$

where K_{cm} is the fracture toughness of the ceramic matrix. A chain of small notched specimens around the tip of a kink is considered in the statistical model as shown in Fig.4. The probabilities of failure and crack deflection can be calculated by using the combined mechanical and statistical models.

DISTRIBUTED DISLOCATION METHOD

The Distributed Dislocation Method (DDM) which has been proposed by Kageyama et al. [6,7] is applied to calculate the mechanical model of toughening as shown in Fig.3. The fundamental solution of DDM is the elastic solution of an edge dislocation in an infinite plate with a crack. Fig.5 shows the coordinate system on the z -plane, that is, $z = x+iy$. x and y represent the real and imaginary parts of z , respectively. When the

Fig.5 Coordinate system

Fig.6 Division of boundary of kink

length of a main crack is sufficiently longer than l_s , the main crack can be approximated by a semi-infinite crack which locates on the negative part of the x-axis. The edge dislocation locates at $z_0=x_0+iy_0$, and b_x and b_y are, respectively, the x and y components of the Burgers vector. The x and y components of total force at $z=x+iy$ are P_x and P_y , respectively. P_x and P_y equal to the forces which act on an arbitrary path Γ from origin to point z .

$$P_x = \int_{\Gamma} (\sigma_{xy} dy - \tau_{xy} dx) \quad P_y = \int_{\Gamma} (\tau_{xy} dy - \sigma_y dx) \quad (3)$$

The complex potentials of the problem can be obtained according to the mirror image principle of Moriguchi [8], and the total forces are given by Eqs. (4) and (5) [6]. The solution exactly satisfies the "stress free" condition on the main crack. E and ν are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the composite materials, respectively. The over bar in Eqs. (4) and (5) represents conjugate complex number.

$$-P_y - iP_x = 2B \log \left[\frac{\sqrt{z} - \sqrt{z_0}}{\sqrt{z} + \sqrt{z_0}} \right] + B \frac{z - \bar{z}_0}{2\sqrt{z_0}} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{z} - \sqrt{z_0}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{z} + \sqrt{z_0}} \right\} - \frac{z - \bar{z}}{2\sqrt{z}} \left[B \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{z} - \sqrt{z_0}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{z} + \sqrt{z_0}} \right\} + \bar{B} \frac{z_0 - \bar{z}_0}{2\sqrt{z_0} (\sqrt{z} + \sqrt{z_0})^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$B = \frac{E'}{8\pi} (b_y - ib_x) \quad E' = E \quad \text{in plane stress} \quad (5)$$

$$= E/(1-\nu^2) \quad \text{in plane strain}$$

The boundary of a kink is divided into N linear segments. The dislocation density is assumed to be continuous and constant within each segment as shown in Fig.6. Eqs.(4) gives the solution of a discrete dislocation. The solution of continuously distributed dislocations can be obtained by integrating Eq.(4). We use 3 Gauss points and obtain a

summation expression. The equivalent distribution of dislocations which satisfies the boundary conditions on the kink is obtained by solving the simultaneous linear equations of equilibrium. The stress method, for example, by Vitek [9] could be used. But the total force method is more preferable than the stress method because the average quantities of boundary conditions along the segments are always satisfied. The value of N have been chosen to be 128 and 256 in the present analysis and an extrapolation technique[6] is used in order to obtain more accurate results.

RESULTS OF MECHANICAL MODEL AND FRACTURE CRITERION

The stress intensity factors at the tip of kink, \bar{K}_I and \bar{K}_{II} , can be represented as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{K}_I &= C_{11}(\theta) \left[K_I - f_1(\theta) \frac{2}{\pi} S_b \sqrt{2\pi l_s} \right] \\ \bar{K}_{II} &= C_{21}(\theta) \left[K_I - f_2(\theta) \frac{2}{\pi} S_b \sqrt{2\pi l_s} \right] \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where K_I is the applied stress intensity factor in mode I. $C_{11}(\theta)$, $C_{21}(\theta)$, $f_1(\theta)$ and $f_2(\theta)$ are functions of θ and calculated by the DDM. The results are shown in Figs.7 and 8. Interpolation functions are obtained from the present analysis in the range of $-90^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11}(\theta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} (1 + \cos \theta) (1 + 0.051 \zeta^4) \\ C_{21}(\theta) &= \frac{1}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \sin \theta (1 - 0.048 \zeta^2 + 0.033 \zeta^4) \\ f_1(\theta) &= f_2(\theta) = f(\theta) = 1 / \cos^2 \frac{\theta}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where $\zeta = \theta/90$ in degree or $2\theta/\pi$ in radian. The errors are less than 0.3% in C_{11} and C_{21} and 0.5% in f_1 and f_2 .

Fig.7 Coefficients C_{ij} in Eq.(6)

Fig.8 Coefficients f_i in Eq.(6)

The closure stress, S_b , is given by the following equation.

$$S_b = Ts \quad (8)$$

where s is the density of pullout fibers and T is the pullout force.

$$T = (\pi/2) d l \tau \quad (9)$$

Where d and l are the diameter and length of a fiber, respectively. The frictional shear stress is assumed to be constant on the interface between a fiber and matrix, and τ denotes the critical shear stress. The effective length of a pullout fiber is chosen to be $l/2$.

A fracture criterion for CMC proposed by Marshall[2] is modified and extended to the mixed mode fracture because the kink is subject to the mixed loading of modes I and II. An effective stress intensity factor, K_{eq} , is proposed in the present analysis in order to satisfy the fracture criterion given by Eq.(2).

$$K_{eq} = q_1 \frac{E_m}{E} \sqrt{h_1(\theta)} \left[K_I - f(\theta) \frac{2}{\pi} Ts \sqrt{2\pi l_s} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$h_1(\theta) = C_{11}^2(\theta) + C_{21}^2(\theta) \quad (11)$$

E_m is Young's modulus of the matrix and E_m/E represents an effect of load transfer. q_1 represents the effect of crack impediment, that is, the interaction of a crack front with fibers and is given from the line tension model[10]. $h_1(\theta)$ denotes a coefficient of energy release rate in kinking[7]. The results of $h_1(\theta)$ are shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9 Coefficient h_1 in Eq.(10) as a function of θ

ANALYSIS OF STATISTICAL MODEL

As random distributions of the locations and directions of fibers are assumed, the average density of pullout fibers, s_{av} , is given according to Fullman's[11] calculation, where β_c denotes the critical pullout angle.

$$s_{av} = (2/\pi) V_{pf}/d^2 \quad (12) \quad V_{pf} = P\beta(\beta_c) V_f \quad (13)$$

$P\beta(\beta_c)$ is the probability that the angle between a fiber and the normal

direction of the fracture plane is less than β_C .

$$P\beta(\beta_C) = (1 - \cos 2\beta_C)/2 \tag{14}$$

V_{pf} gives the volume fraction of pullout fibers.

The region ($l_s \times l_s$) is divided into m small cells. An equivalent intersecting area of a fiber, A_{eq} , is introduced as follows,

$$A_{eq} = V_{pf}/s_{av} = (\pi/2)d^2 \tag{15}$$

As A_{eq} is assumed to be the size of cells, m is given by the following equation.

$$m = l_s^2/A_{eq} = s_{av}l_s^2/V_{pf} \tag{16}$$

The probability that a pullout fiber exists in a cell is V_{pf} . Hence, the probability, $P(n)$, that n pullout fibers intersect the area ($l_s \times l_s$) is given as binomial distribution.

$$P(n) = mCn(V_{pf})^n(1-V_{pf})^{m-n}, \quad mCn = m!/[n!(m-n)!] \tag{17}$$

By using Stirling's formula, if m and n are large,

$$n! = \sqrt{2\pi} n^{n+1/2} e^{-n} \tag{18}$$

and as the density of pullout fiber, s , equals to n/l_s^2 , the distribution density function, $f_s(s)$, is given by

$$f_s(s) = \frac{l_s}{\sqrt{2\pi s_{av}}} \frac{(s_{av}/s)^{l_s^2 s + 1/2}}{\sqrt{1-V_{pf}s/s_{av}}} \left[\frac{1-V_{pf}}{1-V_{pf}s/s_{av}} \right]^{\frac{l_s^2 s_{av}}{V_{pf}}(1-V_{pf}s/s_{av})} \tag{19}$$

Fig.10 Effect of V_f on the shape of distribution function of the density of pullout fibers. This figure shows examples in the case of $s_{av}=50000/\text{mm}^2$, $P\beta(\beta_C)=1$ and $l_s=100\mu\text{m}$.

If V_{pf} converges to zero, Eq.(19) coincides with Poisson's distribution. The variance of s is $s_{av}(1-V_{pf})/l_s^2$. The effect of V_{pf} on the shape of the distribution function is shown in Fig.10.

The cumulative distribution function $F_S(s)$ is defined by

$$F_S(s) = \int_{-\infty}^s f_S(t) dt \quad (20)$$

From Eq.(10), the cumulative distribution of K_{eq} at given K_I and θ is obtained as follows,

$$F_K(\xi | K_I, \theta) = 1 - F_S \left(\frac{K_I - \frac{E}{q_1 E_m \sqrt{h_1(\theta)}} \xi}{f(\theta) \frac{2}{\pi} T_s \sqrt{2\pi l_s}} \right) \quad (21)$$

where ξ represents random variable of K_{eq} . When the probability density function of K_{cm} is $f_m(\eta)$, the probability of failure, $F_\theta(Kc, \theta_i)$, at $K_I = Kc$ and $\theta = \theta_i$ is calculated from the following formula.

$$F_\theta(Kc, \theta_i) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f_m(\xi) \{1 - F_K(\xi | Kc, \theta_i)\} d\xi \quad (22)$$

A chain of notched specimens, as shown in Fig.4, is considered in the statistical model. The probability of failure, $F_C(Kc)$, of the ceramic composite system is given by

$$1 - F_C(Kc) = \prod_i [1 - F_\theta(Kc, \theta_i)] \quad (23)$$

The distribution of fracture toughness can be estimated from Eq.(23). Increment of angle θ is chosen of such a value of $\tan^{-1}(3l/(l_s^2 \sqrt{s_{av}}))$ from a statistical consideration.

EXAMPLES OF ANALYSIS

Normal distribution of K_{cm} is assumed in the present analysis. A SiC whisker/ Al_2O_3 composite is chosen for the numerical example. The properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Properties of SiC Whisker/ Al_2O_3 composites analyzed

Fiber	diameter (d), 0.8 μ m	length (l), 25 μ m
Matrix	fracture toughness (K_{cm}), 4.2MPa \sqrt{m}	
Vf	30%	
Parameters	l_s 30mm	β_c 30°
	E/E_m 1.2	q_1 1.0

Fig.11 shows the effect of pullout force on the probability of failure. The fracture toughness of composites, Kc , is normalized by a mean value of fracture toughness of matrix, K_{cm} . K^* represents a normalized pullout force, $(2/\pi) T_{s_{av}} \sqrt{2\pi l_s} / K_{cm}$, and coefficient of variation

(COV) of the fracture toughness of matrix is 0.2 in Fig.11. The effect of COV is shown in Fig.12, where K^* is chosen to be 1.0. Fig.13 represents the probability of crack deflection at several K_c/K_{cm} values. The crack deflections take place more easily as the applied load increases. Fig.14 shows the relations between V_f and K_c/K_{cm} . The lower bounds of error bars denote 95% reliability of K_c . $\tau=270\text{MPa}$ is assumed in the analysis. This value is about 30% of theoretical value [5].

Fig.11 Effect of pullout force on the probability of failure.

Fig.12 Effect of COV of matrix on the probability of failure.

Fig.13 Probabilities of crack deflection are shown with a parameter of K_c/K_{cm} . ($K^*=1.0$ and $\text{COV}=0.2$)

Fig.14 Relation between mean value of normalized fracture toughness and V_f

CONCLUSIONS

Effects of the crack deflection and fiber pullout on fracture toughness are examined by using the Distributed Dislocation Method. A statistical distribution of the number of pullout fiber on the fracture surface is proposed and applied to the statistical model of toughening. The combined effects of crack deflection and fiber pullout are examined in the statistical model and the probability of failure of ceramic matrix composites is obtained.

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